

turntable at 25 ml/pot at 5 days after transplanting. Each treatment was replicated twice. The sprayed plants were allowed to dry for 1 hour. Twenty brachypterous BPH females in the 1st experiment and 20 5th-instar GLH nymphs in the 2d, were caged on treated plants with a glass tube covered with muslin. The exposure periods were 1, 2, 4, and 6 hours for BPH and 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 hours for GLH. Mortality was recorded after the exposure periods. Moribund insects were treated as dead. For mortality in the control, the corrected percentage of mortality in the treatment was calculated by Abbott's

LT₅₀ and LT₉₀ values of pesticides against the brown planthopper and green leafhopper. Bhopal, M.P., India.

Pesticide	Conc (% active ingredient)	Values (h)			
		Brown planthopper		Green leafhopper	
		LT ₅₀	LT ₉₀	LT ₅₀	LT ₉₀
Control	0	—	—	—	—
Methyl parathion	0.025	3.5	5.0	1.6	2.0
Quinalphos	0.025	2.4	5.0	1.5	2.2
Phosphamidon	0.025	2.6	4.0	1.5	2.4
Carbaryl	0.05	2.0	3.0	1.25	1.8
BPMC	0.05	< 1.0	1.0	0.8	1.1
BPMC + carbaryl (1:1)	0.05	1.1	1.8	0.6	0.9
Landrin	0.05	2.0	3.0	1.5	2.5

formula and plotted on log-probit paper against time in hours; graphical Lethal Time (LT₅₀) and Lethal Time 90 (LT₉₀)

were calculated for the different insecticides (see table). ■

Leaf folder control through interference in chitin biosynthesis

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The effect on larvae of the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* Guenee of a new insecticide Dimilin (R)—with a unique mode of action on insects was studied. Dimilin (diflubenzuron) interferes with chitin biosynthesis and deposition in the insect cuticle. Interference in chitin deposition in the insect exoskeleton leads to inhibition of molting.

Potted TN1 rice plants were sprayed with 200 ppm Dimilin with a hand atomizer. When the spray fluid dried up, final-instar larvae of the leaf folder were released on plants confined in cylindrical

Morphogenetic changes in leaf folder larvae that fed on Dimilin®-treated rice leaves. A: normal pupae; B: pupae with deformed proboscis; C & D: larval-pupal mosaics. Tamil Nadu, India.

polyester cages. The larvae which fed on Dimilin-treated plants formed silken webs, but were unable to molt and develop into pupae (see figure). The insecticide caused deformities: pupae with deformed proboscis and larval-pupal mosaics. The pupal deformities are evidently due to interference in chitin

deposition. In all the 5 replications of 10 larvae each, 80% of the test insects were deformed. The result suggests that Dimilin—a new generation of insecticide—has the potential to control the rice leaf folder through physiological inhibition of chitin deposition. ■

Irrigation and water management

Effect of irrigation regimes on agronomic characters of rice

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The effects of different irrigation regimes on agronomic traits of the semidwarf rice variety Cauvery were studied in a greenhouse trial. Continuous flooding

was the superior irrigation regime in its influence on grain yield and nutrient recovery, but it did not improve the harvest index. Yield and nutrient recovery performance was poor in rice plants grown under continuous saturated conditions. Flooding at the reproductive stage was found to increase yield, nutrient recovery, and harvest index more

than flooding at the vegetative stage.

Nutrient recovery was closely associated with yield but harvest index was an independent trait and differed from yield trends. Harvest index decreased successively in the following order of irrigation regime: I₂, I₁, I₄, I₃ (see table). The highest harvest index in treatment I₂ was probably because of proper equi-